

LATEST DISCOVERIES IN THE TREATMENT OF UTERINE MYOMA, INDICATIONS FOR SURGICAL TREATMENT.

Kurbanova Surayyo Ilxom qizi

Obstetrician-gynecologist of the 4th family polyclinic of Mirzo Ulugbek district
kurbanovasurayyo1992@gmail.com

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Belgian scientists have worked to create a new drug that fights fibroids, which will help avoid hysterectomy in cases of significant progression of fibroids. As a result of research, a new generation of tablets - Esmya medicinal preparations - was developed. The active substance of this drug is ulipristal acetate. This compound is the basis of many emergency contraceptives and has a selective modulatory effect on progesterone receptors.

When it became known that the formation and development of myoma depends not only on the estrogen background, but also on the progesterone content, scientists raised the issue of finding substances that eliminate the effect of progestogens on the body. Thus, a group of biologists at the Saint-Luc hospital of the University of Brussels decided to investigate the effect of ulipristal acetate on the development of fibroids that do not respond to conservative treatment. To study the effect of the drug, 550 female volunteers who required surgery for the treatment of fibroids were recruited. The experiment lasted 3 months. After reviewing the obtained results, the scientists noted that Esmya™ drug significantly contributed to reducing the size of myoma and reducing the severity of the clinical symptoms of the disease..

Such information is encouraging for doctors and many patients suffering from this disease. Perhaps, soon the treatment of uterine fibroids will be very easy and quick. Instructions for surgical treatment of uterine fibroids

Prompt surgical intervention for the treatment of fibroids is indicated in the following cases:

- Many nodules, myoma more than 12 weeks and crushing small pelvic organs;
- Strong and frequent bleeding from the uterus;
- The growth rate is more than 4 weeks per year;
- Myomatous node necrosis;
- Registration of uterine fibroids together with adenomyosis;
- Submucosal nodule formation;
- Twisting of the subserous node legs;
- Submucosal fibroids.

Depending on the type of myoma, severity of the disease, location and other individual characteristics, the surgeon determines the method of myomectomy. It

should be mentioned that if a woman is advised to operate on a fibroid, laparoscopy or hysteroscopy are the methods that protect the body and preserve reproductive potential. Then the recovery period of the body will be as fast as possible, and the ability of the woman to save the uterus and be able to get pregnant will be preserved.

Uterine artery embolization Embolization, that is, blocking the uterine arteries, is an excellent method of treating fibroids, and it has great potential. To carry out such a procedure, it is necessary to insert a special probe into the uterus and find a certain vessel that supplies blood to the myomatous node of the uterus. Then special substances are injected into this artery that cause vascular embolism. The nutrition of the tumor stops and gradually the tumor can be absorbed. Unfortunately, this operation is not suitable for all fibroids, and the consequences of such treatment and the risk of recurrence of the disease have not been fully studied. However, most doctors have a positive opinion and even say that a woman can get pregnant and carry a fetus after such a procedure. It should be remembered that the issue of preserving the reproductive function in each patient is individual.

Although myoma often does not show any symptoms or is manifested, but does not cause discomfort, women often put aside the diagnosis and treatment. Ignoring this part of the body is very dangerous. The disease can take the form of a low-quality tumor, which leads to uncontrolled growth and very unpleasant treatment, as well as many other unpleasant consequences.

Due to the growing problem of early diagnosis of pathologies of the female reproductive system, the number of women undergoing hysterectomy (removal of the uterus) due to fibroids detected at a late stage is increasing. This surgical intervention causes many unpleasant consequences and is a great stress for the woman's body. Unfortunately, in this case, the reproductive function cannot be implemented.

If surgical treatment is optimal from a medical point of view, a woman should think about her health first. In a woman's body, the uterus serves only to give birth to a child, and even without this organ, a woman can live a long and full life.

If the patient has children, the moral side of the problem is easily solved. Nevertheless, even if a woman does not have children, it is not necessary to risk her life and health in order to preserve this possibility. If an operation is recommended, it means that the process cannot be stopped by other means and the loss of this organ is inevitable. One should not forget the possibility that the tumor will turn into a bad-quality tumor.

